

Synthesis and Spectral Studies on Metal Chelates of Heterocyclic Carboxaldehyde Thiosemicarbazones[†]

P. UMAPATHY*, A. P. BUDHKAR and C. S. DORAI

National Chemical Laboratory, Poona-411 008

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Square-planar neutral metal chelates of aldehyde thiosemicarbazones of the type ML_2 , where $M = Ni^{II}$, Pd^{II} or Pt^{II} and $HL =$ thiosemicarbazone or 4-phenyl- or 4-methylthiosemicarbazone of 2-furaldehyde or thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde or *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, have been synthesised and characterised. Ir, uv-visible, 1H and ^{13}C nmr and polarographic techniques have been utilised to study and characterise the free ligands and their metal chelates. The data suggest that the heterocyclic carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazones exist predominantly in thioenol form in DMSO solutions or in solvents with pH ~ 7.7 and above. The ligands act as N, S bidentate chelating agents coordinating through the nitrogen(I) and the thiolate sulphur atom.

THE α -(*N*)-heterocyclic carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazones constitute a class of agents which possess both antineoplastic and antiviral activity¹. The first compound to be examined for biological activity, 2-formylpyridine thiosemicarbazone, was shown to possess mild antileukemic activity against L-1210 tumour in mice at levels of drug which produced significant toxicity^{2,3}. The biological activity of this class of compounds is associated with chelation, and direct correlation between anti-tumour activity and chelating ability of several of these compounds was shown by Michaud and Sartorelli⁴. Similarly, the mode of antiviral action of methisazone, (1-methylisatin- β -thiosemicarbazone), the first synthetic antiviral drug, is initially thought to be metal chelation^{5,6}. There are many thiosemicarbazonecopper(II) complexes which have significant antitumour activity⁷⁻⁹.

While remarkable progress in understanding the activity of these compounds has been made by biological methods, the chemistry remains obscure in detail. Furthermore, pyridine and isoquinoline are the two heterocyclic ring systems which have been most extensively investigated^{9,10} for structure-activity relationships. Thiosemicarbazones of other available ring systems have not been to any extent explored. In an effort to gain more insight into the nature of bonding and stereochemistry present in this class of compounds, metal chelates of ligands with carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone side chain α to an unencumbered ring oxygen (sulphur) of heteroaromatic character, as well as *ortho*-substituted-aromatic carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazones have been synthesised and studied. Ir, uv-visible, 1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra and polarographic techniques have been used to characterise free ligands and their metal chelates, and the results of the study presented.

Experimental

K_2PtCl_4 and Na_2PdCl_4 were prepared by the reported methods¹¹. The ligands, 2-furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone, 2-furaldehyde-4-methyl thiosemicarbazone, 2-furaldehyde-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazone, thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone, thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde-4-methyl thiosemicarbazone, thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazone, *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazone were prepared by a general method¹², condensing thiosemicarbazide with an aldehyde in equimolar quantities in aqueous alcoholic medium in presence of glacial acetic acid (1-2 ml). The crude products obtained were purified by repeated recrystallisation from chloroform or alcohol.

2-Furaldehyde, thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde, *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, thiosemicarbazide, 4-methyl thiosemicarbazide and 4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide and $DMSO-d_6$ were from Fluka (A.G.), Buchs (S.G) or Aldrich. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Solvents were purified and dried prior to use.

1H nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian FT-80A spectrometer. Spectra were also recorded on a Varian T-60 spectrometer. The experimental conditions for the FT-80A nmr spectrometer were concentration 2-5% in $DMSO-d_6$ or $CDCl_3$; sample tube diameter, 5 mm; SW=1 000 Hz; internal standard, $(CH_3)_4Si$. ^{13}C nmr spectra were run on the same spectrometer at 20.0 MHz with proton noise decoupling. For 1H nmr decoupled spectra, the parameters were SW=6 000 Hz; concentration, saturated solutions in $DMSO-d_6$, sample tube diameter=10 mm. All the spectra were measured at room temperature. Infrared spectra (nujol or hexachlorobutadiene) were recorded on

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a Pye-Unicam SP300 spectrophotometer. The solution spectra, however, were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 221 spectrophotometer. The ultraviolet and visible spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP8-100 UV-VIS spectrophotometer. Polarograms were recorded on a 174A (PAR) polarographic analyser Model in combination with PAR 303 static mercury drop electrode. The working electrode was a dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) and the reference electrode was Ag/AgCl and the counter-electrode was platinum wire. Samples were purged with N_2 for 20 min before recording the polarograms. All measurements were performed at 25–27°. The DPP was recorded with a 50/20 mV modulation/amplitude, 1 drop s^{-1} , 2 mV s^{-1} scanning rate. The deuterio analogues were prepared by either refluxing with D_2O (99.8%, Atomic Energy Commission, Bombay) or with acetonitrile and D_2O under N_2 atmosphere, followed by evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure.

Nickel chelates were synthesised by mixing aqueous alcoholic solutions of nickel chloride hexahydrate and the corresponding heterocyclic carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in alcohol in 1 : 2 mole ratio. In the case of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone, hot methanol was used. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to 7.0 or slightly above with the addition of dilute ammonia (1 : 3). The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 1 h and the solid products (green to brown) were collected on a filter under suction, and washed repeatedly with water followed by hot ethanol (2 × 5 ml) and dried. Pt^{II} and Pd^{II} chelates (yellow to orange) were isolated essentially in the above manner. The yields of the crude products were generally 90%.

The analytical data for the ligands and their metal complexes are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone and other heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones studied, exist in the thioketo form in the solid state as evidenced from the infrared spectral data. Bands attributable to SH vibrations are absent. All compounds showed N—H stretching modes of vibration as well as strong bands in the region 1 570–1 395, 1 420–1 260 and 1 140–700 cm^{-1} , assignable to C=S stretching vibration¹⁴. The lack of consistency in their position confirms the view that in the compounds in which the thiocarbonyl group is linked to nitrogen, strong vibrational coupling effects are possible. In solution, however, thiosemicarbazones can exist in the thioketone (A) and thioenol (B) forms, the latter being favoured in alkaline solution.

In the deprotonated form they are potentially bidentate ligands coordinating through 1-nitrogen and the thiolate sulphur atom forming five membered chelate rings¹⁵.

M = Divalent metal ion

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	M.p / decomp. temp. °C	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)				Metal
			O	H	N	S	
1.	2-Furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone, 2-furtsco	156–57a	43.26 (41.60)	4.63 (4.14)	23.54 (24.85)	19.46 (18.93)	—
2.	Bis(2-furaldehydethiosemicarbazonato)-nickel(II)	250	36.60 (36.49)	3.26 (3.04)	20.05 (21.28)	15.97 (16.21)	15.07 (14.87)
3.	Bis(2-furaldehydethiosemicarbazonato)-palladium(II)	251	32.51 (32.68)	3.08 (2.72)	18.43 (18.93)	13.17 (14.46)	24.25 (24.10)
4.	Bis(2-furaldehydethiosemicarbazonato)-platinum(II)	247	27.69 (27.11)	2.78 (2.26)	15.50 (15.81)	13.27 (12.05)	36.40 (36.74)
5.	2-Furaldehyde-4-methylthiosemicarbazone, 2-furmethytso	163	45.72 (45.90)	5.21 (4.92)	22.00 (22.95)	16.25 (17.49)	—
6.	Bis(2-furaldehyde-4-methylthiosemicarbazonato)-nickel(II)	255	39.21 (39.74)	4.08 (3.79)	19.00 (19.87)	15.72 (15.14)	14.07 (13.89)
7.	2-Furaldehyde-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone, 2-furphenytso	181–82	58.88 (58.78)	4.90 (4.49)	16.12 (17.14)	12.35 (13.06)	—
8.	Bis(2-furaldehyde-4-phenyl-thiosemicarbazonato)nickel(II)	254	52.48 (52.68)	3.85 (3.66)	14.60 (15.36)	10.40 (11.71)	11.05 (10.74)
9.	Bis(2-furaldehyde-4-phenyl-thiosemicarbazonato)palladium(II)	265	48.35 (48.45)	3.54 (3.86)	13.60 (14.13)	11.33 (10.77)	18.27 (17.90)
10.	Bis(2-furaldehyde-4-phenyl-thiosemicarbazonato)platinum(II)	235	48.24 (42.16)	3.42 (2.93)	11.75 (12.30)	—	29.13 (28.56)

(Table 1 contd.)

11.	Thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemi-carbazone, Thioph ₂ sc	190-91	39.10 (38.92)	4.11 (3.78)	21.66 (22.70)	33.29 (34.59)	—
12.	Bis(thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemi-carbazonato)nickel(II)	257	34.05 (33.75)	3.10 (2.81)	18.33 (19.69)	—	12.82 (13.76)
13.	Bis(thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemi-carbazonato palladium(II)	278	30.74 (30.35)	2.86 (2.53)	16.33 (17.71)	25.55 (26.98)	23.41 (22.43)
14.	Bis(thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemi-carbazonato)platinum(II)	276	26.08 (25.57)	2.89 (2.13)	13.69 (14.92)	—	34.96 (34.65)
15.	Thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde-4-methyl-thiosemi-carbazone, Thioph-4-methyl ₂ sc	158-59	43.74 (42.21)	4.55 (4.52)	19.58 (21.10)	31.24 (32.16)	—
16.	Bis(thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde-4-methyl-thio-semicarbazonato)nickel(II)	231	37.90 (36.94)	3.92 (3.52)	17.67 (18.47)	—	12.54 (12.91)
17.	Thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde-4-phenyl-thio-semicarbazone, Thioph-4-phenyl ₂ sc	198	55.64 (55.17)	4.51 (4.21)	15.13 (16.09)	23.11 (24.52)	—
18.	Bis(thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde-4-phenyl-thio-semicarbazonato)nickel(II)	220	48.98 (49.77)	4.05 (3.46)	14.37 (14.52)	—	9.40 (10.04)
19.	Bis(thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde-4-phenyl-thio-semicarbazonato)palladium(II)	215	46.09 (45.98)	3.70 (3.19)	12.64 (13.41)	—	16.31 (16.99)
20.	Bis(thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde-4-phenylthio-semicarbazonato)platinum(II)	267	39.58 (40.27)	3.08 (2.80)	—	—	28.34 (27.28)
21.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone, <i>o</i> -nitrobenz ₂ lsc	245	42.31 (42.86)	3.77 (3.57)	24.05 (25.00)	18.62 (14.28)	—
22.	Bis(<i>o</i> -nitrobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazonato)-nickel(II)	250	38.97 (38.04)	3.17 (2.77)	21.94 (22.19)	11.11 (12.68)	11.62 (11.63)
23.	Bis(<i>o</i> -nitrobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazonato)-palladium(II)	252	35.28 (34.76)	3.13 (2.53)	—	10.55 (11.59)	19.71 (19.26)
24.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazone, <i>o</i> -nitrobenzal-4-phenyl ₂ sc	212	56.28 (56.00)	4.29 (4.00)	18.85 (18.66)	9.33 (10.66)	—
25.	Bis(<i>o</i> -nitrobenzaldehyde-4-phenylthiosemi-carbazonato)nickel(II)	253	51.79 (51.16)	3.68 (3.35)	16.46 (17.05)	8.28 (9.75)	9.01 (8.94)
26.	Bis(<i>o</i> -nitrobenzaldehyde-4-phenylthiosemi-carbazonato)palladium(II)	258	48.40 (47.70)	3.78 (3.12)	15.52 (15.90)	8.54 (9.08)	15.98 (15.11)
27.	Bis(<i>o</i> -nitrobenzaldehyde-4-phenylthiosemi-carbazonato)platinum(II)	288	42.11 (42.37)	3.23 (2.77)	—	—	25.05 (24.60)

Refs. 12, 13.

TABLE 2—¹H Nmr SPECTRAL DATA OF HETEROCYCLIC CARBOXALDEHYDE THIOSEMICARBAZONES AND THE METAL CHELATES

Sl. no.	X	R	Solvent	Metal	Heterocyclic ring protons/phenyl				—OH = δ(ppm)	N(2)H/SH	N(4)H	
					3'	4'	5'	phenyl				
1.	O	H	DMSO-d ₆	—	6.76 6.73	6.42 6.40 6.38 6.46	7.5	—	7.77	11.22	7.98	7.4
2.	O	H	DMSO	—	6.9	6.6	7.7	—	8.0	11.0	—	7.5
3.	O	C ₆ H ₅	DMSO	—	6.7	6.6	7.1	—	8.1	11.77	—	9.8
4.	O	C ₆ H ₅	CDCl ₃	—	6.72 6.78	6.47 6.53	6.94	7.3- 7.69	7.2	10.62	9.94	9.12
5.	S	H	DMSO	—	—	—	—	—	8.0	11.12	—	7.85
6.	S	C ₆ H ₅	CDCl ₃	—	6.69 6.94	6.45 7.0	6.94 7.03	7.25- 7.63	7.2	10.03	9.0	8.03
7.	O	H	DMSO	Ni ^{II}	—	—	—	—	7.2	—	—	7.1
8.	O	C ₆ H ₅	DMSO	Ni ^{II}	—	—	—	—	7.4	—	—	9.6

The infrared spectra in chloroform solution of 2-furtsc, 2-fur4phenytsc and thioph₂sc show medium to weak/weak-broad bands at 2 564—2 538 cm⁻¹ region due to ν_{SH}. Confirmation of this assignment was forthcoming from the weak bands observed at 5 180—5 019 cm⁻¹ ascribable to its first overtone band¹⁶. In the spectra of the corresponding deuterated compounds the bands either

disappeared or shifted. The observed shift for the ν_{SH} in these compounds from the usual SH assignment¹⁷ (2 600–2 550 cm^{-1}) is rather small and is due to inter-/intra-molecularly bonded SH present in solutions. The spectra of 2-furtsc, 2-fur4-phenytsc, 2-fur4methytsc, thioph4methytsc, thiotsc, *o*-nitrobenzatsc in DMSO (dried over CaH_2) show medium/weak and broad bands at 2 550–2 480 cm^{-1} .

The ^1H nmr spectra of heterocyclic carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazones and some of their corresponding metal chelates were recorded in DMSO, DMSO-d_6 or CDCl_3 solutions (Table 2). Solubility problems precluded study of other ligands and chelates. In $\text{DMSO-d}_6/\text{CDCl}_3$, the spectra of the ligands, 2-furtsc, 2-fur4phenytsc and thioph4phenytsc exhibited two resonances (sometimes obscured by that of aromatic protons as in the case of thioputsc) for the $\text{N}(4)\text{H}_2$ protons indicating hindered rotation about the $\text{C}(\text{S})-\text{NH}_2$ bond due to its partial double bond character¹⁸. The nmr spectra of 2-furtsc and 2-fur4phenytsc measured in $\text{DMSO-d}_6/\text{DMSO}$ at various concentrations show, in addition, a sharp singlet at δ 11.22

and 11.77 (Fig. 1). The peak observed for 2-fur4-phenytsc showed marked concentration dependence (moved upfield by 1.20 ppm with higher concentration). The concentration dependence and upfield shift are typical of a thiol group^{19,20}. This signal disappeared either on deuteration or on chelate formation. The presence of a hydrogen bonded chelate ring can be inferred from the downfield position of the signal. However, this could arise also due to a bonded proton attached to a nitrogen atom.

The ^{13}C nmr chemical shift data of 2-furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone and its neutral nickel and palladium chelates are presented in Table 3 (Fig 2). The carbon resonance assignments for C_2 , C_3 , C_4 , C_5 and for (a) are in agreement with those reported in literature²⁴. The replacement of a carbonyl group by a thiocarbonyl group results in a downfield shift. In compounds containing the thio functional group such as in $\text{CH}_3\text{C}(=\text{S})-\text{NH}_2$ and others containing $\text{N}-\text{C}(=\text{S})-\phi$ and $\text{N}-\text{C}(=\text{S})$ group, the carbon resonances are reported at 207.2, $\sim$ 192.8 and

Fig. 1. ^1H nmr spectrum of furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in DMSO-d_6 .

TABLE 3— ^{13}C NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (ppm) OF 2-FURALDEHYDE THIOSEMICARBAZONE AND ITS NICKEL AND PALLADIUM CHELATES

Sl. no.	Compd	Solvent	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	a	b
1.	2-furtsc	DMSO d_6	145.85	118.18	112.66	133.13	149.88	178.49
2.	2-furtsc (deuterated)	DMSO- d_6	145.4	118.86	112.79	133.49	149.51	178.05
3.	Ni(2-furtsc) $_2$	DMSO- d_6	145.13	120.49	112.94	140.85	147.67	174.97
4.	Pd 2-furtsc) $_2$	DMSO- d_6	146.0	121.22	113.75	140.9	147.18	174.68

Fig 2. Proton noise decoupled ^{13}C nmr spectrum of 2-furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in DMSO- d_6 .

at 200 – 206 ppm, respectively^{22, 23}. In the monothio- β -diketones the thio carbonyl carbon resonance is observed at 182.4 ppm²⁴. The sharp signal at 178.49 ppm in the spectrum of 2-furtsc, which on deuteration is reduced considerably with slight upfield shift (178.05 ppm) and on chelate formation

shifted upfield, could reasonably be assigned to the carbon attached to the thiol function (C-SH) rather than to thione carbon (C=S). The significant upfield shift in the neutral Pd and Ni chelates indicates binding to the metal atom through thiolate sulphur (the other binding site being N(1)). It is

noted that the carbon atoms (aldehydic, a) in the chelates are more shielded than the corresponding carbon of the ligand.

Differential pulse polarograms of thiosemicarbazide and 2-furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in alcohol/isopropanol/DMSO solvents buffered with LiCl/phosphate/NaOAc-CH₃COOH were recorded. In anodic dissolution polarography, the current obtained is actually due to the reaction, $2\text{Hg}^0 \rightarrow \text{Hg}_2^{2+} + 2e$. The concentration of mercurous ions produced is a function of the mercaptide concentration. The irreversible dissolution peak for 2-furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone has an $E_{1/2}$ at -0.16 V vs Ag/AgCl in an electrolyte consisting of 0.15 M (Na₂HPO₄+KH₂PO₄) in 40% isopropanol solvent. The half-wave potential for thiosemicarbazide in the same solvent and buffer is at -0.25 V (Fig. 3). The half-wave potentials for several thiols are reported at -0.30 V vs S.C.E.²⁵.

Fig. 3. Differential pulse polarogram of 2-furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in 40% isopropanol-phosphate buffer (pH=7.7).

The observed increase in the negative direction for 2-furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in the $E_{1/2}$ value is attributable to the insolubility of its mercury salt in the organic solvent. No peak corresponding to the presence of C=S in the solution in the range 0.05 – 0.12 V or near 0.00 V, however, could be observed^{26,27}.

The polarographic reduction of thiosemicarbazide and 2-furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in 75% alcohol- 0.1 M LiCl/75% alcohol- 0.2 M (NaOAc-CH₃COOH) gave two well defined diffusion-controlled reduction peaks. Differential pulse polarogram for thiosemicarbazide showed peaks with $E_{1/2}$

at -0.25 and at -0.65 to 0.61 V. In DMSO- 0.1 M LiCl, thiosemicarbazide showed two peaks with $E_{1/2}$ at 0.58 and -0.79 V, while 2-furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone showed only one peak with $E_{1/2}$ at -0.59 V. The absence of the peak with $E_{1/2}$ at -0.79 V suggests the absence of the thioketone form of 2-furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in this solvent. However, in view of the $E_{1/2}$ values reported²⁸ for several thiobenzophenones and other compounds containing C=S group at -0.82 to -0.95 V, one could not unequivocally assign the peak with $E_{1/2}$ in both these compounds at -0.79 V to a C=S group.

The uv-visible spectra of 2-furtsc, 2-fur4phenytsc, 2-fur4methytsc and thiotsc were recorded in different solvents. In alcohol/chloroform solutions, the heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones showed a single broad band with maxima at ~ 320 – 325 nm. The alkaline solutions of the corresponding thiosemicarbazones also showed a single absorption (broad) with a marked shift, with maxima at ~ 335 – 365 nm. Of the two thioketone and thioenol forms, the thioenol form may be assumed to be favoured in alkaline solution²⁹.

The infrared spectra of 2-furtsc, 2-fur4phenytsc, 2-fur4methytsc, thiophtsc, thio4phenytsc, thioph4-methytsc, *o*-nitrobenztsc, *o*-nitrobenz4phenytsc and some of their deuterated analogues and metal chelates of Ni^{II}, Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} were recorded in the 4000 – 200 cm⁻¹ region. $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ is strongly coupled in nearly all the compounds in which the carbon is directly linked to nitrogen. In the spectra of all the ligands, strong absorption bands appearing in the two regions at 840 – 800 cm⁻¹ (shifted slightly on deuteration) and 1100 – 1040 cm⁻¹ attributable respectively to nearly pure $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ coupled with N–C–N stretching³⁰ or N–N stretching and N–C–N deformation vibration³¹, were observed. In the spectra of the corresponding metal chelates, the absorption bands in both the regions disappeared. Appearance of a new sharp band, simultaneously in the region 700 – 600 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$ could be taken as evidence of the ligands coordinating via thioenol structure^{32,33}. An interesting feature is the appearance of a strong band at 900 – 1000 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of all metal chelates assignable to N–N stretching vibration^{33,34}.

In the spectra of all the thiosemicarbazones well defined bands at 3500 – 3000 and ~ 1600 cm⁻¹ were observed. The medium intense bands at ~ 3400 , ~ 3220 and at ~ 3140 cm⁻¹ on deuteration shifted (isotone ratio, 1.3). The band observed in the vicinity of 3400 cm⁻¹ can be ascribed to ν_{NH_2} and the one near 3170 cm⁻¹ to ν_{NH} on the basis of previous assignments³⁵. The strong absorption near 1600 cm⁻¹ ascribable to δ_{NH_2} also shifted on deuteration. A medium to strong band for $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ appears in the 1550 – 595 cm⁻¹ region of the spectra of all thiosemicarbazones which shifts to lower frequencies on coordination with metal

ion, by about $10-15\text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating involvement of N(1) in chelate formation. However, there is likely to be overlap with aromatic ring absorptions in the region.

The infrared spectra of Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} chelates and some of their deuterated analogues at $600-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ showed absorptions which are absent in the spectra of the corresponding ligands. The medium intense bands at $\sim 300-320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are least sensitive to deuteration could arise predominantly due to metal-sulphur stretching modes. In the region $400-470\text{ cm}^{-1}$, two medium intense absorptions were observed. The bands in the higher frequency region are sensitive to deuteration and accordingly the bands at $\sim 430-460\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}^{\text{as}}$.

The electronic spectra of Ni^{II} chelates with 2-furtsc, 2-fur4methytsc, 2-fur4phenytsc, thiophytsc, thioph4phenytsc, and Pt^{II} and Pd^{II} chelates of 2-furtsc have been recorded in chloroform solution. The spectra of nickel chelates exhibit two absorptions at ~ 1750 and 21500 cm^{-1} due to γ_2 and γ_3 transitions, respectively, which may suggest square-planar configuration around Ni^{II} ions³⁹⁻⁴². Generally, γ_3 and γ_2 are tentatively assigned to ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{3g}$ and ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{1g}$ transitions, respectively. Above 20000 cm^{-1} region there are two very intense bands. The lowest energy band can be assigned to $\text{L} \rightarrow \text{M}$ charge transfer transition while the highest energy band at $\sim 32000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is probably due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ of the ligand. Due to limited solubility, the spectra of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} chelates with 2-furtsc were not well resolved in the visible region. The bands at $\sim 41500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\text{Pd}(\text{2-furtsc})_2$ and at $\sim 42000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\text{Pt}(\text{2-furtsc})_2$ could be assigned to internal ligand transitions, $\text{L}(\pi) \rightarrow \text{L}(\pi^*)$. The intense bands observed at $\sim 31500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in both the chelates are $\text{L} \rightarrow \text{M}$ charge transfer bands⁴³. The $d \rightarrow d$ bands are obscured by the more intense charge transfer bands. The spectra of the chelates do not show any absorptions in the near infrared region. From the similarity in the spectral characteristics, with reported square-planar complexes^{38,43,44}, it may be inferred that Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} chelates with heterocyclic carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazones possess square-planar geometry.

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